

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF ORGANIZING SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10574730>

Abstract: This article contains thoughts and opinions on the organization of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions. Information is given about achievements, shortcomings, problems and their solutions in the field of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions in Uzbekistan, educational processes in organized events.

Key words: spiritual and educational works, educational institutions, national, events, spirituality, enlightenment, creativity, human value, education, spiritual need, worldview.

As a result of comprehensive reforms and creative works implemented in our country, our people's consciousness and worldview are changing. In our country, the importance of the life-giving idea "From national revival to national rise" is increasing more and more in the establishment of a legal state and civil society.

Despite the important work carried out in this regard, a number of systemic problems remain, which hinder the effectiveness of spiritual and educational reforms in the process of updates in the social, economic and political spheres.

In the current era of globalization, specific socio-spiritual and spiritual changes occurring in the consciousness of young people require a complete revision of the work in the educational system from the point of view of modernity, importance and efficiency, effectiveness. .

In order to increase the knowledge and level of young people, expand their worldview, and actively support talented students, a number of contests and sports competitions are regularly held in educational institutions. All these works are being organized within the framework of the existing systems and mechanisms that have been formed so far. In addition, the work in the spiritual and educational sphere has not lost its importance in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, and modernity.

Nevertheless, in today's era of globalization and fast information, the role of social networks and mass media in the management of the state and society has been dramatically activated due to the freedom of speech in line with the democratic reforms in our country. At such a time, there was a need to raise the education of young people to a new level. Of course, in order to work and

achieve results in such a complex situation, first of all, conditions and highly qualified personnel are needed.

In particular, there is no integrated system for the organization of spiritual-educational processes, insufficient organizational-practical and scientific-research work is being carried out to protect our people, especially young people, from spiritual threats, in this direction, state organizations, Social cooperation of educational institutions, civil society institutions, mass media and the private sector has not been effectively established.

The analysis shows that in the following years, some young people think of benefiting the nation, the Motherland, and the feeling of becoming a useful person in strengthening independence is not formed on a special, scientific basis. the feeling is manifested. At the same time, among some students, there are unpleasant manifestations such as spiritual limitation, being deceived by foreign ideas due to a narrow worldview, non-observance of national etiquette standards, a gap between words and deeds, and a lack of national pride. , it is necessary to study and eliminate them on a scientific basis.

From this point of view, in order to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions, the 2020 year of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Law No. ORQ-637 of September 23 "On Education", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 "New "O" for the years 2022-2026 Decree "On Development Strategy of Uzbekistan", Decision PQ-5040 dated March 26, 2021 "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the System of Spiritual-Educational Affairs", in the course of updates in the social, economic and political spheres, the ground was created for the increase in the effectiveness of spiritual and educational reforms.

As it can be seen from these decisions, the fate of the economic reforms being carried out in our Republic is ultimately an important vital problem. The reason is that the main task of spiritual and educational work is to educate a perfect person who embodies high moral qualities. Today, only educated, well-qualified, highly intelligent and visionary entrepreneurs can accelerate the progress of our society towards world civilization and ensure that Uzbekistan occupies a worthy place among the developed countries of the world. Raising spirituality and enlightenment, which is the basis of strengthening the independence of Uzbekistan and building a new society, and developing it consistently based on the requirements of the present time, based on the roots of our national spirit, is an urgent and extremely important task of today.

In fact, the main goal in the implementation of spiritual and educational work is to meaningfully spend free time of young people, to satisfy their spiritual and aesthetic needs, to enrich their spiritual world, to develop feelings of patriotism, dedication, and hard work, to contribute to the development of society. Great goals have been set, such as taking his place, becoming an active member of society in the future, becoming knowledgeable, intelligent, and intelligent.

Currently, it is necessary to organize youth education based on uniform systems and mechanisms in accordance with the conditions created in educational institutions. For this, it is appropriate to focus on current tasks, problems and their solutions in the field. Already, recent events related to students show that there are issues that need to be resolved.

First, it is becoming more and more clear that the one-sided, boring and "patterned" traditional spiritual and educational activities held in educational institutions are not justified today. The level of participation of students in these events is very low and you can always see the same contingent. Therefore, it is not mandatory to organize spiritual and educational activities, but it is important to pay special attention to the students' wishes and interests.

Secondly, in fact, the biggest problem in the spiritual and educational field is the wide scope of the field, the abstractness of the educational methodology, and the lack of scientifically based criteria and indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of educational work. Due to the fact that the employees responsible for the organization of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions often organize the work for the farmer, and transfer the activities only in the name of the report, the achievement of results is reduced to the second level. The wide coverage of the spiritual and educational sphere, the repeated or numerically large number of tasks given by high-ranking organizations, the involvement of students in mandatory activities without taking into account the wishes of the students, the absence of a clear boundary and a single work program in the field do not allow for the systematic organization of work. .

Thirdly, the increase in the number of students and pupils led to a lack of classrooms in educational institutions. Now, almost all state higher education institutions have switched to two-shift study. As a result, at the expense of creating additional auditoriums, spiritual and educational spaces (sports facilities, library, cultural centers, media center, spiritual rooms) that help to meaningfully organize free time of students and pupils in educational institutions. is decreasing.

Fourthly, we are lagging behind in terms of the content and level of information young people receive through social networks. Today, we must take into account that social networks have become a big pulpit, and young people are being educated by those who come to this pulpit. Of course, the impact of social networks on the consciousness of 100,000 of our youth cannot be compared with the event held by educational institutions in the hall of activists for 100-200 students. If we do not carefully study the negative impact of the information distributed on social networks on the education of young people, if we lag behind this process, there is a great possibility of a significant gap in the spiritual and educational sphere. Therefore, it's time to seriously study, analyze and research the impact of social networks on young people, and on this basis, to put an end to the old-fashioned, ineffective, dry lecture events organized in auditoriums.

Fifth, to teach students to be proud of their chosen educational institution from the day they arrive at educational institutions, to create a healthy environment, to establish a cordial relationship between students and professors, "mentor", Being worthy of the high status of "student of a higher educational institution" in all respects, achieving responsibility and demonstrating high moral quality in oneself are among the important issues.

Sixth, in order to prevent the recent unpleasant situations and tragedies related to assassinations in educational institutions, it is necessary to assess the mental and psychological condition of students and pupils, to diagnose their problems, and on this basis to carry out the necessary psychodiagnostics, treatment and prevention work. we need to start.

Seventh, to study, analyze and analyze the existing problems in the spiritual and educational education of students and to develop the necessary methodological recommendations for the officials of the field based on this basis, to develop education in the educational system. there is a need for the activity of "mind centers" that determine the priority directions of spiritual and educational work.

In conclusion, it should be said that purposeful organization of spiritual and educational work with specific goals in mind, inculcating the spirit of love for the Motherland in the minds of people, improving the social and spiritual environment among them, building them with confidence for tomorrow The importance of this activity is incomparable in attracting them to their work, raising their morale, and growing them to become knowledgeable, educated, conscientious people.

References:

1. Prezident Sh.Mirziyoyevning 2021-yil 26-martdagi “Ma’naviy-ma’rifiy ishlar tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-5040-son qarori. Yangi O‘zbekiston. www.lex.uz
2. Prezident Sh.Mirziyoyevning Yoshlarni ma’naviy-axloqiy va jismoniy barkamol etib tarbiyalash, ularga ta’lim-tarbiya berish tizimini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga ko‘tarish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risidagi Qarori. // Xalq so‘zi. 2018-yil, 15- avgust
3. Otamurodov S. va boshqalar. “Ma’naviyat asoslari” T. “Ma’naviyat”, 2002y.
4. Жабборов, Ж.А. (2021). Интерпретация проблемы духовных потребностей в научных исследованиях ученых нашей страны. Общество и инновации, 2(5/S), 484–491. <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss5/S-pp484-491>
5. Жабборов, А. М., Жабборов, И. А., & Жабборов, Ж. А. (2015). ЭТНИЧЕСКИЕ СТЕРЕОТИПЫ И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ САМОБЫТНОСТИ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (1), 80-83.
6. Жабборов, А. М., & Жабборов, Ж. А. (2016). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УЗБЕКСКИХ НАРОДНЫХ ПОСЛОВИЦ ПРИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ УЧЕБНО-ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (3), 93-95.
7. Жабборов Ж.А. Маънавий эҳтиёжлар – жамият тараққиётининг мезони // «Трансформация суспільних наук: соціально-економічний, лінгвістичний, політичний та іт-виміри» II Міжнародна наукова конференція. 22.10.2021. Харків, UKR. 40-43 бет. <https://doi.org/10.36074/mcnd-22.10.2021>
8. Жабборов Ж.А. Ўзбекистонда таълим-тарбия тизимини объектив заруратга мослаштириш бўйича олиб борилаётган давлат сиёсати. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. (6), 2021 y. 19-28 b.
9. Жабборов Ж.А. Илм-фанда эҳтиёжлар таснифи. Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-29.10.2021.v1.34>
10. Жабборов Ж.А. Постмодерн жамият зиддиятларининг маънавий эҳтиёжлар юксалишига таъсири (фалсафий таҳлил). Традиційні та інноваційні підходи до наукових досліджень, 149.
11. Жабборов Ж.А. Мамлакатимиз олимларининг илмий тадқиқотларида маънавий эҳтиёжлар муаммосининг талқини // Жамият ва инновациялар

– Общество и инновации – Society and innovations Special Issue – 5 (2021) / ISSN 2181-1415. Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 = 5.395. Б. 484-491.

12. J.J. Azimovich. Analysis of spiritual needs. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary ..., 2021.

13. Egamberdiyev J. SOCIO-HISTORICAL GENESIS OF IDEAS THAT FORM THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF YOUTH. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development. –P. 426-432.

14. Jabbarov J.A. INTERPRETATION OF NEEDS IN THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 633–636.

